

Instructional leadership as a catalyst for organizational commitment: insights from a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

This research intends to provide insight on the relationship between instructional leadership and organizational commitment, with a specific emphasis on the timeframe spanning from 2009 to 2023. Using the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) approach, this study conducted a systematic search of academic databases, including Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, and ERIC. The search produced a large selection of papers, reviews, and articles about organizational commitment and instructional leadership. The analysis demonstrated the critical role that the impact of instructional leadership on organizational commitment played by using an advanced search strategy involving keywords, such as “instructional leadership,” “educational leadership,” “school leadership,” “organizational commitment,” “employee commitment,” and “workplace commitment.” The review identified three main themes from the final dataset, which included 33 items. These themes were: i) instructional leadership and teachers; ii) organizational commitment and school leadership styles; and iii) leadership in diverse educational contexts. The key themes were then validated by experts. The analysis reveals school leaders’ potential contributions to organizational commitment, which has consequences for educational leadership and management.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the disciplines of organizational studies and education, the impact of instructional leadership on organizational commitment is a topic that receives a lot of attention. Many research investigations have looked into the relationship between organizational commitment and instructional leadership, shedding light on how different leadership philosophies, organizational cultures, and other factors influence how committed people are to their organizations [1]. The concept of organizational commitment encompasses the psychological attachment and the sense of loyalty employees feel towards their organization. Organizational commitment is a disposition among individuals to maintain their membership in an organization due to their fervent desire to contribute to its well-being and derive advantages from its values and objectives [2]. It is influenced by various factors, including leadership styles, organizational culture, and the alignment of personal and organizational values. In the context of education, where the turnover rates are notably impactful on student outcomes, understanding and fostering organizational commitment is paramount.

Within the discipline of instructional leadership, various studies have employed systematic literature review (SLR) to investigate the correlation between instructional leadership and organizational commitment.

Hallinger and Heck [3] emphasize that effective instructional leaders actively engage in defining school missions, managing the curriculum, and promoting a positive school culture, which are crucial for improving teacher commitment and organizational performance. For instance, Dewi [4] undertook a systematic literature study to analyse instructional leadership techniques in schools, emphasizing the relevance of instructional leadership in managing changes in the education sector. Prastyo and Hidayat [5] discovered that instructional leadership enhances organizational commitment and job satisfaction among lecturers. This emphasizes the wider influence of instructional leadership on the commitment and satisfaction of academic personnel, so contributing to the overall atmosphere inside the organization. This highlights the significance of instructional leadership in influencing organizational commitment through its impact on academic outcomes.

The past study also discovered that, in comparison to transactional leadership style, transformational leadership style significantly influences organizational commitment. This reveals how various leadership ideologies affect organizational commitment in different ways, with transformational leadership having a bigger influence. Furthermore, a study conducted by Dewi [4] investigated the impact of transformational and instructional leadership on teachers' job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The findings revealed that job satisfaction plays a mediating role between these two factors. examined how teachers' job satisfaction and organizational commitment were affected by transformational and instructional leadership, demonstrating that job satisfaction acts as a mediator between the two. Furthermore, several researches [6], [7] illustrated how employee work culture and organizational cynicism function as moderating factors in the positive effects of transformative leadership on organizational commitment. Additional research demonstrating the significance of virtual instructional leadership in fostering organizational commitment discovered that principals' virtual instructional leadership practices had a positive effect on teachers' commitment in schools. This finding shows how organizational commitment may be directly impacted by leadership style.

Moreover, other studies [8], [9] emphasize the indirect beneficial impact of principal instructional leadership on organizational commitment. This impact is achieved through increased teacher satisfaction and motivation, which in turn enhances teachers' involvement in school activities. This implies that instructional leadership has a direct impact on organizational commitment and also influences it by affecting teacher commitment and satisfaction. This body of evidence suggests that the role of instructional leaders extends beyond pedagogical oversight to include shaping an environment that nurtures the commitment and professional unity essential for achieving educational excellence.

Literature is quite insightful about the impact of instructional leadership on organizational commitment. It also reveals the complexity of this construct and the fact that aside from instructional leadership, job satisfaction, career development, and organizational justice also feature into the level of organizational commitment. Thus, this paper is dedicated to reviewing available literature on instructional leadership and organizational commitment. This system review is expected to present a clear picture of how instructional leadership impacts organizational commitment. By synthesizing relevant studies, this review seeks to deepen insights into how instructional leadership influences organizational commitment within educational settings, contributing to the existing knowledge base on this topic.

The preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) approach helps researchers find, select, and combine studies on the issue. The novelty of PRISMA-based research on organizational commitment and instructional leadership resides in the transparent and exhaustive methodology utilized to collect, evaluate, and report prior studies. Using this approach, the study hopes to give empirical support for the gaps found and provide a clear path forward for further research in this field. "What is the fundamental connection between organizational commitment and instructional leadership?" is the overarching question that guides this review. This study will help educators, administrators, and policymakers aiming to elevate the quality of education.

2. METHOD

For the purpose of writing this review, the authors followed the recommendations that were established by PRISMA. Researchers may guarantee that the literature highlights they provide are of the highest caliber by using the PRISMA model, which allows them to process information step-by-step [10]. According to Mengist *et al.* [11], there are four stages involved in creating articles using the PRISMA approach: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion. The PRISMA approach is a framework for conducting systematic reviews and meta-analyses that prioritizes transparency and repeatability [12]. The process entails devising a protocol, establishing criteria for eligibility, doing an extensive literature search, choosing relevant studies, extracting data, evaluating the risk of bias, combining data, and presenting the findings in a structured format. By following the PRISMA technique step by step, researchers can perform methodologically sound, transparent, and reliable systematic reviews and meta-analyses, ultimately contributing to evidence-based decision-making in a variety of academic domains.

2.1. Identification

For the purpose of selecting several pertinent papers for this study, the three main stages of the systematic review process are applied. The initial stage in the process is to identify your keywords and hunt up relevant terms in dictionaries, thesaurus, encyclopedias, and previous research. For the databases, Scopus, ERIC, and Web of Science (WoS) search strings have been created as shown in Table 1, once all pertinent phrases were found. WoS, Scopus, and ERIC were chosen as key databases for conducting a SLR because they provide comprehensive and authoritative coverage of scholarly publications across a wide range of fields. WoS and Scopus are well-known for their vast indexing of peer-reviewed journals across a wide range of scientific and social sciences disciplines, ensuring a diverse choice of research papers and high citation data quality. Furthermore, Scopus and WoS use recognized procedures such as the PRISMA, which ensures a systematic and scientific approach to the review process [13]. ERIC, on the other hand, is a specialized resource that is particularly useful for researchers who are doing SLR in the field of education. It provides essential information and support for researchers working in educational contexts [14]. During the initial phase of the systematic review process, 113 publications were successfully obtained from all the databases that were used for the inquiry that is currently being conducted.

Table 1. The search string

Database	Search string
Scopus	TITLE - ABS - KEY (("instructional leadership" OR "educational leadership" OR "school leadership") AND ("organizational commitment" OR "employee commitment" OR "workplace commitment")) AND PUBYEAR > 2008 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND (LIMIT - TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT - TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT - TO (PUBSTAGE , "final"))
ERIC	("instructional leadership" OR "educational leadership" OR "school leadership") AND ("organizational commitment" OR "employee commitment" OR "workplace commitment")
WoS	("instructional leadership" OR "educational leadership" OR "school leadership") AND ("organizational commitment" OR "employee commitment" OR "workplace commitment") (Topic) AND 2009-2023 (Year Published) AND Article (Document Type) AND English (Language)

2.2. Screening

The first phase of the study consisted of the rejection of 15 papers based on particular exclusion and inclusion criteria that were meticulously developed by the authors as presented in Table 2. The research articles were the major criteria for inclusion because of their significance as the primary source of information that is applicable to real-world situations. The study specifically excluded certain publishing forms, including books, book series, chapters, general reviews, meta-analyses, meta-syntheses, systematic reviews, conference proceedings and press status. Additionally, the review focused solely on articles written in English. It is important to note that the method was created throughout the course of the past 15 years (2009-2023), during which time a total of 15 articles were eliminated based on specific criteria. The following stage involved the meticulous removal of 12 duplicate papers.

Table 2. Search selection criteria

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Timeline	2009-2023	<2009
Literature type	Journal (article)	Book, proceeding, review
Publication stage	Final	In press

2.3. Eligibility

A total of 101 articles have been created for the eligibility phase, which is the third step. Each article's title and main body were carefully examined at this stage to ensure they met the inclusion criteria and complemented the goals of the current investigation. As a result, 68 reports were disregarded since they did not contain pertinent area articles supported by empirical data. As a result, a total of 33 papers were chosen for further consideration.

2.4. Data abstraction and analysis

In this study, mixed, qualitative, and quantitative research designs were combined using integrative analysis. To create themes on organizational commitment and instructional leadership, the writers examined 33 studies. As can be seen in Figure 1, the authors conducted a comprehensive review of a collection of 35

articles in order to identify assertions or information that was pertinent to the subjects of the study. The three primary themes were instructional leadership and teacher outcomes, organizational commitment and school leadership styles and leadership in diverse educational contexts. The writers worked with coauthors to establish themes based on observations, maintain documentation for analysis, and settle disputes. Next, two experts rewrote the topics to make sure they were adequate, clear, and significant. Based on professional suggestions and input, adjustments were made. The analysis and selection procedure to determine the authenticity of the concerns was carried out by two experts: a specialist in human resource development and a leadership expert with expertise in education leadership and training.

Figure 1. Flow diagram for the recommended search research [15]

3. RESULTS

Three primary themes about the relationship between organizational commitment and instructional leadership were found as a consequence of the review. School leadership styles, organizational commitment, and instructional leadership and teacher outcomes were the three key themes. Tables 3-5 display the results of key themes, respectively.

Table 3. A simplified table of studies included in the systematic review (theme 1: instructional leadership and teacher outcomes)

No	Authors	Title
1	Chen <i>et al.</i> [16]	Effects of school principals' leadership behaviors: a comparison between Taiwan and Japan
2	Hallinger <i>et al.</i> [17]	Do beliefs make a difference? Exploring how principal self-efficacy and instructional leadership impact teacher efficacy and commitment in Iran
3	Qadach <i>et al.</i> [18]	Instructional leadership and teachers' intent to leave: the mediating role of collective teacher efficacy and shared vision
4	Çoğaltay and Karadağ [19]	The effect of educational leadership on organizational variables: a meta-analysis study in the sample of Turkey
5	Pietsch <i>et al.</i> [20]	On the differential and shared effects of leadership for learning on teachers' organizational commitment and job satisfaction: a multilevel perspective
6	Thien <i>et al.</i> [21]	(Re)Investigating the pathways between instructional leadership, collective teacher efficacy, and teacher commitment: a multilevel analysis
7	Sarikaya and Erdoğan [22]	Relationship between the instructional leadership behaviors of high school principals and teachers' organizational commitment
8	Niqab <i>et al.</i> [23]	Instructional leadership potential among school principals in Pakistan
9	Khan <i>et al.</i> [1]	Instructional leadership and students academic performance: mediating effects of teacher's organizational commitment
10	Febriantina <i>et al.</i> [24]	Impact of school principals' transformational leadership and teacher's organizational commitment on their citizenship behaviour

Table 4. A simplified table of studies included in the systematic review (theme 2: organizational commitment and school leadership styles)

No	Authors	Title
1	Sukarmin and Sin [8]	The influence of principal instructional leadership behaviour on the organisational commitment of junior high school teachers in Surakarta
2	Berkovich and Eyal [25]	Emotional reframing as a mediator of the relationships between transformational school leadership and teachers' motivation and commitment
3	Benoliel <i>et al.</i> [26]	School principals' systems thinking antecedents and consequences
4	Hulpia <i>et al.</i> [27]	The relation between school leadership from a distributed perspective and teachers' organizational commitment: examining the source of the leadership function
5	Dou <i>et al.</i> [28]	The effects of autonomy gap in personnel policy, principal leadership and teachers' self-efficacy on their organizational commitment
6	Kırkıç and Balci [29]	Organizational commitment levels of preschool teachers and administrators' leadership styles
7	Berkovich [30]	Effects of principal-teacher gender similarity on teacher's trust and organizational commitment
8	Ford <i>et al.</i> [31]	The effects of leader support for teacher psychological needs on teacher burnout, commitment, and intent to leave
9	Qader and Benoliel [32]	The implications of principal leadership styles on teachers' organizational commitment in the Israeli Arab educational minority
10	Aydin <i>et al.</i> [33]	The effect of school principals' leadership styles on teachers' organizational commitment and job satisfaction
11	Amzat <i>et al.</i> [34]	Principal leadership style and teacher commitment mediated by teacher wellbeing in Islamic Schools in Malaysia
12	Nobile and Bilgin [35]	A structural model to explain influences of organisational communication on the organisational commitment of primary school staff
13	Cilek [36]	The effect of leadership on organisational commitment: a meta-analysis
14	Tran <i>et al.</i> [37]	Effects of principals' leadership styles on teachers' commitment in Vietnam
15	Sukarmin and Sin [38]	School health as the mediator variable: determinants of the principal instructional leadership behavior
16	Benoliel <i>et al.</i> [26]	School principals' systems thinking: antecedents and consequences
17	Awang <i>et al.</i> [39]	The influence of virtual instructional leadership on teachers' commitment: a Malaysian e-leadership case study
18	Liu and Werblow [40]	The operation of distributed leadership and the relationship with organizational commitment and job satisfaction of principals and teachers: a multi-level model and meta-analysis using the 2013 TALIS data
19	Berkovich and Eyal [25]	Emotional reframing as a mediator of the relationships between transformational school leadership and teachers' motivation and commitment

Table 5. A simplified table of studies included in the systematic review (theme 3: leadership in diverse educational contexts)

No	Authors	Title
1	Scott and Dixon [41]	Partners in a learning organization: a student-focused model of professional development
2	Nurhuda <i>et al.</i> [42]	Retrospective of five years research of school leadership in Asia (2018–2022): a scientometric paradigm
3	Al-Mahdy [43]	'Much ado about something' how school leaders affect attitudes towards inclusive education: the case of Oman

4. DISCUSSION

The objective of this research was to investigate, through an experimental design, how organizational commitment in learning environments is impacted by the dynamics of instructional leadership under principal direction. The findings have indicated a favorable correlation, underscoring the crucial role that leaders play in establishing and nurturing their organizations' dedication. The research yielded three primary themes: leadership in diverse educational contexts, organizational commitment and school leadership styles, and instructional leadership and teacher outcomes. Each theme adds something unique to our understanding of how complicated instructional leadership is. The discussion that follows allows for the drawing of conclusions.

4.1. Theme 1: instructional leadership and teacher outcomes

The findings shed light on the crucial role that instructional leadership plays in forming the outcomes of teachers and improving school performance across a wide range of educational and cultural contexts. A collaborative approach to instructional leadership improves student performance in Taiwan and teacher professionalism in Japan, with cultural differences affecting leadership styles [44], [45] found that in Iranian primary schools, the self-efficacy of administrators and the instructional leadership of teachers have a positive influence on the teachers dedication and group efficacy. Qadach *et al.* [18] found differences between Jewish and Arab schools in Israel. Kilag and Sasan [46] showed that committed workers are more content at work and students achieve more when they have strong leadership. Rodulfa [47] discovered a

relationship at the school level between teacher dedication and collective efficacy, with a considerable impact on teacher commitment coming from instructional leadership. The instructional leadership of administrators affects teachers' organizational commitment, which in turn affects students' academic progress. Transformational leadership of school principals also influences teachers' organizational citizenship behavior. Customized strategies are needed to promote positive outcomes and school success. These results show the need for customized strategies that take cultural and contextual variations into account and emphasize the role that instructional leadership plays in promoting positive teacher outcomes and school success.

4.2. Theme 2: organizational commitment and school leadership styles

The research titled organizational commitment and school leadership styles examines the relationship between principals' leadership philosophies and the level of commitment in the educational system. The findings suggest that certain leadership styles, particularly those that are collaborative and inclusive, are more effective in fostering a sense of commitment and belonging among staff members. This has profound implications for how leadership training and development programs are structured for aspiring and current school principals. A study by Prempeh and Kim [48] determined that principal instructional leadership has a moderate and quantitative impact on teacher organizational commitment. Additionally, as a result of transformational school leadership, it has been found that teachers' affective organizational commitment and autonomous motivation are mediated by emotional reframing. This shows that emotional reframing and self-motivation may have an indirect role in the link between commitment and leadership [49]. Research findings suggest that the application of systems thinking has a beneficial effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. It works as a mediator in the connection between instructional leadership and these outcomes [50]. Furthermore, supportive leadership quality, collaboration within the leadership team, and participatory decision making have been recognized as influential elements in teachers' organizational commitment [51]. The research findings show the leadership philosophies of Islamic school principals significantly impact the well-being of Malaysian teachers and act as a partial mediator in the connection between teachers' organizational commitment and their leadership philosophies [52]. This shows how important it is to look at how leadership functions interact with stakeholders. For a full understanding of the factors involved, these results show that the connection between school leadership types and organizational commitment is complex and has many layers.

4.3. Theme 3: leadership in diverse educational contexts

The topic "leadership in diverse educational contexts" illustrates the critical nature of contextual and cultural responsiveness in the practice of leadership. This topic is relevant to this study because the data that emerged from the research process revealed that instructional leadership is only effective when it is contextual and applicable. A leader must be able to respond to the realities of the community to which they are providing leadership. It emphasizes the need for principals to be aware of and responsive to the cultural, social, and economic diversity within their schools. In varied educational environments, leadership is essential to bringing about beneficial changes in the teaching and learning environment. Strong organizational commitment and strong educational leadership are necessary for the successful implementation of reforms, according to research, which highlights the importance of school leadership research [53], [54]. Within the educational system, organizational commitment serves as a mediator between principal leadership styles and teachers' perspectives on inclusive education [55]. Transformational leadership also increases organizational commitment, demonstrating that leadership is vital for promoting it [56], [57]. Furthermore, the significance of leadership in influencing teacher performance and job satisfaction has been highlighted, highlighting the broad implications of leadership styles in educational contexts [58], [59]. In addition, research on innovative behavior and its influence on the performance of public sector organizations has called attention to the importance of entrepreneurial leadership and how it interfaces with a creative, innovative environment [60]. According to the results, leadership is having an important role in the nurturing of a supportive learning environment, and in the process, different leadership philosophies and attitude reflect on the teachers and the extent to which they are dedicated to the organization itself and to their educational productivity.

5. CONCLUSION

Conclusively, this research significantly advances our comprehension of how principle instructional leadership affects organizational commitment. It emphasizes the varied character of leadership in educational contexts, as well as the importance of principals being adaptable, culturally sensitive, and committed to promoting positive teacher outcomes. These findings are crucial for developing future educational policy and leadership training programmed aimed at improving educational quality through effective leadership.

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